

Programme of the meeting

Monday 27.06.2022

15:00 – Registration

19:00 – Dinner and ice breaker

Tuesday 28.06.2022 – Lectures and field trip

10:30–13:00 – Introductory lectures

10:30 – *Damian Moskaiewicz* – The opening of symposium

10:35 – *Wojciech Tylmann* – The welcoming of guests by the Deputy Dean for Research and Development at the Faculty of Oceanography and Geography at the University of Gdańsk

10:45 – *Robert Jan Sokołowski* – Quaternary Stratigraphy of Poland

11:30 – *Piotr Paweł Woźniak* – Introduction to Pleistocene geology and geomorphology of the northern Poland

12:10 – *Maurycy Żarczyński* – Research of lake sediments in Polish Lowlands

13:00 – Lunch break

14:00–18:30 – Field trip (hike) – *Karol Tylmann* – “Geological structure and glaciogenic landscapes of the Kashubian Lakeland”

~19:00 – Evening gathering

Wednesday 29.06.2022 – Presentations and workshops

10:00–13:00 – Participants research presentations

10:00 – *Markas Kazlauskas* – Megafloods and floodscapes of LGM

- 10:20 – *Inese Grīnbauma, Kristaps Lamsters* – Landforms of the Lubāns ice lobe in the Atzele elevated plain
- 10:40 – *Olga Reutt, Damian Moskalewicz, Piotr Paweł Woźniak* – Seeking indicators of tills weathering: How can we exploit geophysical and geochemical methods?
- 11:00 – *Beáta Farkas* – Relict sand wedge sites in Hungary – a sedimentological case study
- 11:20 – Coffee break
- 11:30 – *Shashi Shekhar Shukla, Padmini Pani* – Insights from the Palaeo-Geomorphic Features of the Central Ganga Plain, India: Past to Present
- 11:50 – *Anna Tołoczko-Pasek, Régis Braucher, ASTER Team, Michał Makos* – Determination of the age of carbonate rocks by the cosmogenic chlorine-36, in the valleys of Miętusia and Mała Łąka
- 12:10 – *Marin Mićunović, Sanja Faivre* – Remote sensing applicability in geomorphological investigations of beaches
- 12:30 – *Maciej Kossowski* – Possibilities for the use of drone data in geomorphological analysis of river deltas, based on the delta of Jeziorsko Reservoir
- 13:00 – Lunch break
- 14:00 – *Damian Moskalewicz* – Workshop “Handheld gamma-ray spectrometry”
- 15:30 – Coffee break
- 15:40 – *Karol Tylmann* – Workshop “Dating using TCN”
- ~18:00 – Outdoor geocaching game

Thursday 30.06.2022 – Field trip

9:00–18:00

1. Mechelinki – *Karolina Leszczyńska et al.* – Storm surge deposits at the coastal area (key points: Sedimentological features of storm deposits, reconstruction of palaeostorminess, storm-related landforms)

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2. Rzucewo #1 – *Łukasz Elwirski et al.* – Debris flows in a lacustrine basin (key points: Debris flow and lacustrine sedimentary structures, lithic and soft-sediment clasts distribution, microtomography)

~13:00 – Lunch break

3. Rzucewo #2 – *Piotr Paweł Woźniak et al.* – Geomorphological conditions of early settlement (key points: Holocene evolution of the Puck Lagoon area and their influence on settlement, changes in the availability of local natural resources, stone tool and dugout canoe manufacturing)
4. Dmuchowo – *Aleksandra Jobska et al.* – Weichselian tills with the extraordinary boulder (key points: Glacial sedimentation and deformations, weathering of tills)

~19:00 – Evening gathering

Friday 01.07.2022 – Workshop and closing meeting

9:00 – *Łukasz Elwirski* – Workshop “Microcomputed tomography in Quaternary deposits”

11:00 – INQUA ECR and PWG perspective

11:30 – Lunch

12:30 – Back to Gdańsk